

METHODS, PRINCIPLES AND PRACTICAL PROBLEMS OF STUDY OF "HAMSA" TEXTS BY ALISHER NAVOI

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Annoation: This article analyzes the methods, principles and practical problems of studying the texts of "Khamasa" by Alisher Navoi and the modern methods of textual criticism corresponding to the object of research - conjunctions, glosses and interpolations. This work contributes not only to the use of the results of the contextual studies of the text, but also to the correct interpretation of the literary text, to the understanding of the author's world outlook.

Key words: method, principle, text, textual criticism, work, interpolation, analysis, glosses, conjunctions, literature, words, dictionary.

Since the past centuries, Uzbek classical literature has declared itself, as evidenced by the large research material accumulated in world literary criticism and textual criticism, where the personality of Alisher Navoi stands out, who left his descendants a great literary and scientific legacy.

In the literary wealth of Alisher Navoi, in terms of its volume and significance, the leading position is occupied by "Khamasy" ("Five"). In "Muxokamat ul-lufatayn" ("Litigation of two languages") he himself writes: "I put five fingers on the five of 'Hamsa'. At first, the flowers of my talent were revealed in the garden "Kairat ul-abrar" ("Amazement of the righteous"). The spirit of Sheikh Nizami poured pearls on my head from his "Mahzan ul-asrar" ("Treasury of secrets"). And when my thought turned to the darkness of the charm of "Farhad and Shirin", I lit my lamp from the fire of "Shirin and Khosrov", from the breath of Mir Khosrov. When I turned the feet of love to the valley of "Layli and Majnun", I found precious stones that Khoja Himmati wasted away in "Gavhar-name". When I turned my

heart's gaze to "Sabai Sayyar" ("Seven Planets"), seven beauties from "Khaft Paykar" ("Seven Beauties") of Ashraf appeared before me. When the builder of my soul laid the foundation for "Saddi Iskander" ("Wall of Iskander") the drum of support and assistance thundered from the "Hiradname" ("Book of Wisdom") of his high degree Hazrati Mahdum (Jami)".

This work was studied and studied by such major orientalists as: E.E.Bertels, A.N. Kononov, A.A.Semyonov, S.L.Volin, M.Salye, Gafur Gulyam, S.Ainiy, S.M.Mutallibov, G.K.Karimov, H.Sulaymonov.

However, a detailed study of the originals of the poem by A. Navoi and his scientific treatises suggests that there are still many "blank spots", unexplored, incomprehensible and untranslated words, phrases and expressions, the work on the interpretation of which should be continued. This work requires from the researcher the utmost reliability, therefore, for its conduct, modern methods of conjunction, glosses and interpolation seem to be the most appropriate and appropriate to the object of research.

Conjecture

"Conjectures are important in two respects: for the publication of the text (we will consider this issue later) and for the restoration of the history of the text. The degree of confidence in conjunction varies greatly. Nevertheless, for the history of the text, those conjunctures, the degree of proof of which is very small, may also be important. The author of the well-known work on textual criticism P.Maas considers it necessary to leave in discrepancies to the text all possible conjunctions, believing that as a result of the discovery of new lists, they can ever be confirmed".

D.S. Likhachev writes in this regard: "... The researcher must constantly reckon with the fact that even the most convincing conceptual corrections of seemingly "obvious" errors can sometimes turn out to be false. So, for example, the publishers of the third volume of the "Complete Collection of Russian Chronicles"

(St. Petersburg, 1841) corrected in the Novgorod First Chronicle under 1194. The word “tirovati” on “fat”.

However, in addition to knowledge and, first of all, knowledge of the language, conjunctive corrections require wit and resourcefulness. In this regard, it is the famous scientist V.V. Vinogradov writes: "The very text of the writer's works can be precisely established and correctly read only by those who know well or have deeply studied the language of this writer."

At the present time, the conjecture is mainly given after the publication of the text. Textualists identify errors and shortcomings in a published work based on the meaning of the text. This means that the tasks of the conjunction include correcting errors in sources of various kinds after full understanding and presentation of the lexical and semantic features of the original.

It should also be noted that there are inaccuracies in the published "Khamasa" by Alisher Navoi, for example, there are distortions of the names of some historical figures and a number of subject names. In the following pairs, the first option is right-handed, the second is distortion: محزون маҳзун – махзун (17), ازهر азҳар – азҳар (204), خشن ҳашан – ҳашан (225), خطه хитта – ҳитта (254); خسروآيين хусравойин – ҳусравойин (57), совук – совух (410), تكيه گه такягах – такъягоҳ (406), سخنور суҳанвар – суҳанвар (293), فلاخون фалохун – фалоҳон (306), دوزخ дўзах – дўзах (327), دستکار дасткор – дастгор (218), بي محنت бемехнат – бемиҳнат (227), دماغ димоғ – думоғ (296), محراب меҳроб – миҳроб (370), خروار харвор – харвор (груды; группы) – хирвор-хирвор (238), فلاخن фалохун (праца) – фалоҳан (306), پرده نکتہ нуктапардоз – нукта пардоз (269), فرمان پذير фармонпазир – фармон пазир (277), قصب پوش қасабпўш – қасаб пўш (279), مجلس мажлисорой – мажлис орой (345), حيلت سگال хийлатсигол – хийлат сигол (396), عالم آراي оламорой – олам орой (435), نيم بسمل нимбисмил – ним бисмил (441), پيام آور паёмовар – паём овар (439), نصيحت آميز насиҳатомиз – насиҳат омиз (461), كوھتن ليک кўхтанлик – кўх танлик (284), فکرتانگيز фикратангез – фикрат

ангез (300), اول يان улён – ул ён (282) ; قندخم қадхам – қадхам (104), نوحيز навхез – навхез (25), وضوء вузуъ (очищение) – вузу (35), گنبد гунбад – кунбад (124); اير غاتماق айргатмақ – эрғатмақ (66), روپوش لوغ рўпўшлуғ – рўпўшлиғ (67), محجوب لوغ маҳжублуғ – маҳжублиғ (67), هوش رباى хушрабой – хуш рабой (46); جناحين жанохайн – жанохҳайн (95), اعادى аъоди (й) – аоди (200).

Glosses and interpolations

Gloss - clarifying a difficult word or outdated word, a defect in the text, obscure reasoning. DS Likhachev writes about the restoration and interpretation of the gloss: “The terms“ glosses ”and“ interpolations ”are often used alternatively. It is necessary to distinguish between them as follows. Glossa is a mark in the margins or between the text of a given manuscript. Glossa graphically does not merge with the main text. Interpolation, on the other hand, is an insertion into the text of a work, fused with this text graphically and in essence, although often awkwardly. The scribe himself can make interpolation in the text directly in the process of text correspondence, but more often the interpolation is a glossu rewritten by the scribe ”.

We see exhaustive information from the Uzbek lexicography of the 15th century in the poem by Alisher Navoi. The explanation of the glossy - an incomprehensible word, the root morpheme of their analysis, as well as the scientific attributes of the homonyms in "Muhokamat ul-lughatain" ("Litigation of two languages") can be determined by comparing them with the text of the poem.

About dictionaries of famous works created for Navoi's consideration, Turkologist A.K.Borovkov wrote: “The languages of Eastern Turkestan, the language of Chagatai's dictionary are very rich and interesting as a resource, as a source of historical and cultural significance. In particular, a great contribution to the study of these dictionaries was made by the high artistic skill of Navoi, it contributed to the compilation of dictionaries, dictionaries of these poems in Western Europe ”.

For each of Navoi's poems, dictionaries according to the language of the works are compiled in a certain way. The dictionaries "Hamsa bahalli lugat", "Glossary of Atrakiya", "Glossary of Chagatai and Türko-Usmani" consist of eight or more thousand words. Dictionaries differed in the nature of describing words, order and arrangement according to the alphabet, since they consisted of Arabic, Persian and Turkish lexical units. Such a mechanism - using dictionaries of the language of poems - helps to understand the text of works faster.

A slightly different principle of using dictionaries is used for understanding by Saddi Iskander (Iskander's Wall), Leyli and Majnun, Sabai Sayyor (Seven Planets). "Glossary of Atrakiya" where in the Persian language there are more than 8 thousand words, the two-volume "Glossary of Chagatai and Turkic-Usmani" also has a dictionary of 8 thousand words, although A. Navoi uses only 350 words in his explanations and comments.

Undoubtedly, Navoi dictionaries will contribute to a deeper study of the text of works, category is an important factor in identifying errors and shortcomings. For example, they allow you to edit the "Hamsa", "Saddi Iskander" beit, which looks like this using a dictionary:

Топиб чун қуёш сув юзидин хафо,

Вале партави топмайин интифо.

This raises the problem of determining the suite bay. In the second line, the word "интифо" is not used in the dictionary of Navoi's poem, which raises certain doubts about the appropriateness of its use in this beat. However, in Navoi's dictionary there is "intifo", but in the form of a lateral form of the word انتفا ع intifo (Ъ) - "taking advantage". But this word did not correspond to the essence of the beit, since the inaccuracy made by the calligrapher Abdujamil when copying the text of the poem by A. Navoi took on the meaning of انتفا intifo - "disappearance". In this sense of the word "intifo" does not fit the meaning of the text. But this word can be key in the formation of other manuscripts:

تاپيب چون قو ياش سويوزيدين خفا
ولى پر توى تا پها بين انطفا

The role of Alisher Navoi in the formation of the language of literature and science, in the expansion and enrichment of the dictionary is invaluable. In Uzbek Navoi studies there is a long tradition of creating dictionaries for the works of Alisher Navoi. These dictionaries facilitate the work of translators of the works of the great poet. The most famous of these dictionaries: "Badai-al-lukat" ("Rarities of words") by Tali Imani Herat (XV), "Abushka" ("Old man"), "Sanglakh" ("Rocky place") by Mirza Mahdihan (XIII), Porso Shamsiev and Sobirzhon Ibragimov created the "Concise Dictionary of the Works of Uzbek Classical Literature" (1953) and the "Explanatory Dictionary to the Works of Alisher Navoi" (1972). Batyrbek Khasanov compiled "A Concise Dictionary to the Works of Alisher Navoi" (1993). These dictionaries provide an interpretation of numerous Turkic, Arabic and Persian words from the poet's works. At present, the above-mentioned "Explanatory Dictionary of the Language of the Works of Alisher Navoi" (1983-1985) is considered the most complete. We compared words and expressions from the twenty-volume collection of Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" with the vocabulary of the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Language of Alisher Navoi's Works", as a result of which we identified 1136 (with repetition - 1262) words and expressions that were not included in the explanatory dictionaries. We have given these words a gloss interpretation.

In these dictionaries, interpretations are given to thousands of Turkic, Persian, Arabic words and expressions of the language of the works of Alisher Navoi. So far, the most complete is the four-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Language of Alisher Navoi's Works". Despite the presence of numerous dictionaries on the language of Navoi's works, they do not reflect the vocabulary wealth of the poet. For this reason, this article compares the new words and expressions we have identified from the twenty-volume "Complete Works" of the "Khamsa" (PSS) of the

poet with the four-volume "Explanatory Dictionary of the Language of the Works of Alisher Navoi" (ТСЯПАН) and conducts a textological study. In the work, words and expressions that were not included in ТСЯПАН were selected on the basis of seven principles:

1. In the textual study of words and expressions that were not included in the dictionary, the author relied on the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Language of the Works of Alisher Navoi", recognized as the most complete and perfect to date.

2. In collecting newly revealed words and expressions, we relied on the twenty-volume Collected Works of "Khamsa" by Alisher Navoi.

3. Words and phrases were collected from each volume by reading the text and comparing them with the manuscript.

4. The addressee and the statistics of words and expressions are clearly indicated.

5. Spelling errors in the multivolume edition and the dictionary are corrected on the basis of manuscripts.

6. In this study, the available individual phonetic variants of the words ТСЯПАН are also noted.

7. The work also sometimes presents the lexical or textual meanings of characteristic words that are not given in ТСЯПАН.

The following numerous examples can serve as irrefutable proof of what has been said: چنگزن чангзан (7) (play jew's harp), علي الإطلاق алал-итлоқ (13) (in general, absolutely), معاصي маосий (14) (sinner; innocent), بیک من ذالجلال والإكرام бика мин зул-жалоли вал-икром (18) (prophet), درخشنده дарахшанда (19) (light, bright; brilliant), عزي уззо (19) (title icon), سگ саг (24) (dog), رفراف рафраф (26) (rank, position; place; homeless), хомис (26) (fifth), نعل فام лаълфом (33) (bright ruby; perfect red), حرف بر حرف харф бар харф (42) (literal; letter to letter), عظیمشان азимшон (83) (respected, revered), خطايي زاد хитойизод (85) (Chinese), پурсدا пурсадо (99) (noisy, explosive), مؤذن муъзин (105) (muezzin), دیرکهن дайри кухун

